

Deliverable Report

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Responsible Task Leader	Elżbieta Opiłowska
Authors	Elżbieta Opiłowska, Łukasz Moll, Dorte Jagetic Andersen, Alice Engl, Johanna Mitterhofer, Marcus Nicolson, Eeva-Kaisa Prokkola, Katja Sarmiento-Mirwaldt, Birte Wassenberg
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Executive Summary

This report aims to create a consistent theoretical framework for the B-SHAPES project analyses the impact of borders on people's perception of Europe and the European project. It is argued in the project that narratives play a crucial role in shaping these perceptions, influencing not only people's beliefs and attitudes but also policymaking. The project particularly focuses on narratives associated with the construction of borders and Europe and produced in borderlands. In the first section, the report discusses the main conceptualizations of narratives in the social sciences and their applicability to border studies, encompassing public, spatial, and individual dimensions of narratives. Based on a literature review, the next section elaborates on six master narratives on Europe. B-SHAPES will empirically explore how these macro narratives are reflected in the micro narratives told in the borderlands we study empirically and how they become integrated into people's identities and heritage. We seek to analyze whether and, if so, how borders play a significant role in shaping people's understanding of Europe and Europe's identity. This is investigated through the lenses of Euroscepticism, minorities, and the borderland's natural and cultural landscapes. The report acknowledges that the study of border narratives must consider the fluidity and complexity of narratives and borders, marked by tensions and contradictions.

Introduction

The B-SHAPES project explores borders as factors shaping peoples' perception of Europe and the European project. It starts from the working assumption that perceptions are influenced by narratives that also impact policy making. Narratives affect beliefs, attitudes, intentions, and behaviors of individuals (Braddock and Dillard, 2016). While the report focuses on the conceptualization of narratives in general, we are interested in narratives related to the de-bordering processes. Boswell et al. (2021, p. 8) argue that narratives function as boundary markers that "have the effect of categorizing objects, people, practices and even time and space. [...] Narratives thus play a fundamental role in uniting and separating people, but also in generating feelings of affinity, solidarity and group membership. These distinctions may result not only in symbolic notions of 'Us' and 'Them' but also in influencing and legitimizing social boundaries of inclusion and exclusion, thus determining differential access to civil, social and political rights."

Over recent years the narrative approach has been increasingly employed in international research projects (<https://www.bridges-migration.eu>; <https://i-claim.eu>; <https://www.opportunitiesproject.eu>; <https://ithacahorizon.eu>), however, so far, most

research into narratives is focused on migration narratives. It should be noted that migration narratives are intricately linked with border narratives. B-SHAPES does apply a bottom-up perspective analyzing narratives produced in European borderlands that might be related to migration, but in no way exclusively. Borderlands are often hotspots of crises, as the so-called refugee crisis, Covid-19 pandemic and humanitarian crisis on the Polish-Belarusian borders demonstrated. They are also sites of slow changes and slow multiple disruptions (Svensson and Balogh, 2022). However, they are often ignored in elite politics. Thus, B-SHAPES' goal is to fill the research gap and to include voices of borderlanders.

This report is structured in the following way. The first section discusses the main definitions of narratives in the social sciences and their applicability to border studies by referring to public, spatial and individual dimensions of narratives. In the second part, we review existing scholarly accounts of Europe as a border macro narrative. Although it is up to the project to demonstrate if and how those macro narratives – present in recent research literature on Europe – would circulate in vernacular perceptions of borderlanders, we assume that they could serve as initial interpretative guidelines. Macro narratives selected in the report are widespread not only in specialized literature, accessible only to the researchers, but they are reflected in public debate and common-sense meanings about Europe and its borders (Cantat, 2015, pp. 7-8). As we further demonstrate, macro narratives around the issue of Europe are very often characterized by the border thinking or perception from the border, at the border and – sometimes – beyond the border. According to Bauman (2004) the notion of Europe is unthinkable without the motif of transgressive adventure. Thus, European narratives are specific types of narratives: border narratives. Section two develops the theoretical framework of various border narratives on Europe.

Yet, what are the links between these macro narratives – as they function in politics, media, philosophy or art – and “vernacular border narratives” (Vaughan-Williams, 2021) of borderlanders? The third section is dedicated to establishing the possible links between these two levels where we ask about “Europe as talk and text in everyday life” (Millar and Wilson, 2007): how borders can be experienced by its dwellers, in what way they are visible and embodied in their life-worlds, or what special role they play in perceiving Europe? And how are borders internalized by subjects (Menjivar, 2014), inscribed in physical and mental infrastructures – from landscape to identity, from administrative border lines and border crossings to their internal and affective dimensions, as they are felt in social life? Emphasis is placed on three change agents that were stressed in the project proposal: Euroscepticism, minorities and landscapes as natural and cultural heritage. When and how does living at the border reinforce or weaken Eurosceptic attitudes? In what way are perceptions of Europe mediated by and felt through cultural and natural heritage in borderlands? And, finally, does belonging to a minority in the borderland influence different views on Europe?

Finally, the concluding section considers another challenge for our project: contemporary border transformations in Europe. Given the fact that borders are constantly reshaped and renegotiated – in the context of migration, war, pandemics, Brexit, securitization, or climate

change – it is not enough to treat borders as given factors that shape the perception of Europe. Rather, borders should be understood as variable and dynamic entities, and it is their changing shapes that shape the shape of Europe in people’s perception (Cooper, 2017). In studying the border narratives on Europe from below and in the borderlands, we must be prepared for dealing with floating and flexible meanings, marked by tensions, inconsistencies and contradictions. The multi-dimensional crisis of European borders and their open-ended character might result in various strategies of narration on the side of the researched subjects: from temporal and spatial mapping of ongoing transformations to the desperate attempts to re-establish and confirm the old categories as pillars of ontological security and orientation in the world.

This report aims to create a consistent theoretical framework for the analysis and interpretation of the various narratives we identify in our empirical studies. However, this framework would need constant joint reflection along the subsequent phases of empirical research to avoid the risk of imposing the established assumptions onto the collected sources. It is likely that there will be gaps detected in the project – such as a gap between macro narratives identified in the literature and recent micro narratives created by the borderlanders. It might also be possible that the circulation of some narratives on Europe will be reflected in micro narratives, and some will be absent. But the two most general convictions could be adopted as our working guidelines: (1) that there is an intrinsic link between narratives on Europe and border narratives (Balibar, 2009b), (2) if so, then border transformations in Europe should result in changing narratives on Europe, especially in the borderlands (De Genova, 2017). To put it differently, new tendencies in “(re)bordering and (de)bordering” (Yuval-Davis, Wemyss and Cassidy, 2019) of Europe as a spatial entity influences new perceptions of Europe as lived experience of borderlanders. In the concluding part we will propose how to make our research sensitive to and aware of border transformations and how they influence our understanding of European narratives as border narratives.

1. The narrative approach in the social sciences

During the last decades, the narrative approach has become increasingly important in the social sciences (Czarniawska, 2004) yet its conceptualisation remains elusive. There are no “self-evident categories on which to focus as there are with content-based thematic approaches, or with analyses of specific elements of language” (Squire, Andrews and Tamboukou, 2013). The increased interest in narratives in the social sciences “coincided with a turn away from positivist paradigms towards a more social constructivist approach, which favored qualitative methods and a focus on discourse” (Boswell et al., 2021, p. 5). Czarniawska (2010, p. 59) explains the “narrative turn” in the humanities and social sciences by the claim that firstly narrative knowledge is the main bearer of knowledge in contemporary societies;

secondly an enacted narrative is the most typical form of social life and thirdly, narratives are a common mode of communication. Squire et al. (2014, p. 1) in turn justify the popularity of narrative research in social science with the claim that it “promises new fields of inquiry, creative solutions to persistent problems, a way to establish links with other disciplines such as cultural and literary studies, enhanced possibilities of applying research to policy and practice, and a fresh take on the politics of social research”. They offer a broad inclusive definition of a narrative as “a set of signs, which may involve writing, verbal, or other sounds, or visual, acted, built, or made elements that similarly convey meaning. For a set of such signs to constitute a narrative, there needs to be movement between signs, whether this occurs in sound, or reading, or an image sequence, or via a distinct spatial path, that generates meaning. Because a narrative progresses in this way, it does not only expound, but explains; it is therefore distinct from description.” (Squire et al., 2014, p. 5).

Furthermore, Moen (2006) points out three underpinnings of narrative research: first, human beings organise their experiences of the world into narratives; secondly, narrative researchers maintain that the stories that are told depend on the individual’s past and present experiences, her or his values, the people the stories are being told to, the addressees, and when and where they are being told; the third claim concerns the multivoicedness that occurs in the narratives. Against this backdrop, narratives can be found everywhere (Barthes, 1975). They are present in the media, in political communication, and in the way individuals and groups describe their beliefs, attitudes, identities and histories (Boswell et al., 2021, p. 6). Apart from words, narratives are also explored through pictures, spatial artifacts, and sounds (Hoffmann, 2010). Polletta and Calahan (2019, pp. 57, 68) emphasize that narratives have characters “that are human or human-like in their traits or perceptions”, have events that “follow along the lines of generic plots”, are allusive (make a normative point). Stories’ persuasive power lies in their ability to call up other compelling stories and to build collective identity.

Drawing on multiple definitions, Jones and McBeth (2010, p. 329) define a narrative as “a story with a temporal sequence of events unfolding in a plot that is populated by dramatic moments, symbols, and archetypal characters that culminates in a moral to the story.” Moreover, by taking the structural methodological approach, they conceptualize the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) and identify two dimensions of narrative: form and content. The former includes the following components: setting or context (legal, social and geographic environment), plot (maps the relationships among characters), characters (victims, villains and heroes), and moral of the story (refers to the ethical aspect of the policy) (Jones and McBeth, 2010, pp. 340–341; Jones and Radaelli, 2015)

Scrutinising theoretical conceptualisations of narratives, the project BRIDGES (cf. Garcés-Mascareñas, 2021) propose a comprehensive definition of narrative that are “attempts by actors to develop and convey plausible accounts and interpretations of a phenomenon, event or series of events, person or a group of persons. Narratives are not only simple descriptions. By definition, narratives are characterized by a certain degree of stability and consistency over time

and/or across space. They include assumptions about causality, good and bad, responsibility and consequences. Though narratives must fit with available facts (thus meet certain basic conditions of consistency and plausibility) and need to be understandable and compelling, they can be representationally inaccurate (and recognizably so) and include a contradictory set of beliefs. In fact, their very semantic and/or moral ambiguity may provide appeal to various actors.”

Based on the literature review, B-SHAPES follows the phenomenological approach in narrative studies which concentrates on the subject's perspective, who decodes, interprets, and constructs social reality (Kulas, 2014, pp. 116–118) and not on the text and its structure which is typical for structuralism (Czarniawska, 2004). Moreover, it employs narrative not as a temporal sequence of events but follows the ‘composite strategy’ (Pollastri et al., 2017, pp. 4374–4375). It will reconstruct people’s stories not in any chronological sense, but following ‘kairotic time’ (that is, time punctuated by meaningful events) (Czarniawska, 2010, p. 61): “complete stories (...) begin to emerge, as the actors and the observers connect separate events and actions into a plot leading to a point.” It is thereby able to integrate the three dimensions of perception - chronoception, spatial perception, and sense of agency - and to capture narratives in their social and cultural context, focusing more on the process of their creation than on the structure of a narrative as a closed text to reconstruct the repertoire of stories and the collective knowledge about Europe, the European project and heritage in borderlands. Thus, it will focus not only on the ‘what’ and ‘where’ of a narrative (content), but also on the ‘how’ (the cultural, political, and social context, the producers, and the recipients). Moreover, ‘absence’ will be taken into consideration, as the silent voices that have never been made real as narratives. From this perspective, attention will be devoted to a narrator as a subject who connects all elements into a whole and who decides which elements could be omitted or kept silent (Rosner, 2006, p. 51). As Boje argues “the storytelling did not appear in concise sequences of storytellers recounting full texts to passive listeners [...] people told their stories in bits and pieces, with excessive interruptions of story starts, with people talking over each other to share story fragments, and many aborted storytelling attempts” (Boje, 1991, pp. 112-113).

It should be noted that narratives have many functions. They help people deal with complex social reality on cognitive level by supporting the process of organizing and understanding of social phenomena. Besides, they also have an emotional function by creating shared meaning and facilitating collective solidarity to legitimize collective beliefs, emotions and actions (Boswell et al., 2021). Social actors can strategically manipulate social meanings, for example through portraying certain groups as undeserving or deviant (Jones and Radaelli, 2015).

Following various dimensions of narratives as identified by Somers (1994), B-SHAPES employs three dimensions of narratives: public, spatial and individual as proposed by Dolińska, Niedźwiecka-Iwańczak and Opiłowska (2021) and regards European master narratives, which might be also called macro narratives, and national public narratives as a context (cf. Figure 1). It should be also noted that spatial narratives can be both public and individual.

Figure 1: Narratives’ dimensions (cf. Dolińska, Niedźwiecka-Iwańczak and Opiłowska 2021).

Public narratives are those “attached to cultural and institutional formations larger than the single individual, to intersubjective networks or institutions” (Somers, 1994, p. 619). They function on various scales that may be local, regional, national, and/or global. They are “not neutral; they shape and are in turn shaped by particular understandings of the world which tend to prioritize one meaning over another” (Phibbs, 2008, p. 48) and are used for distinct reasons. Policy actors use narratives to “strategically craft policy narratives to resonate with the public, relevant stakeholders, and governmental decision makers” (Shanahan, Jones and Mcbeth, 2011, p. 536, cited in Boswell et al., 2021, p. 8). Thus, narratives do political work. Stories are created for specific recipients to convince and persuade, and also sometimes to mislead (Riessman, 2008, pp. 8–9).

Public narratives are strongly associated with politics, including spatial politics. Furthermore, they “provide information on how policy, power, territoriality, and collective identity are framed by revealing the prevailing power-embedded hegemonic narratives and counter narratives” (Ackleson, 2001, p. 131). They are dynamic, constantly changing, and dependent on many variables—the producers, their positioning, the political situation, European and

global events, and social changes. Public narratives often refer to individual experiences and narratives, and vice versa. By emphasizing the role of narratives as a tool of political actors to construct a reality and to call for actions, Boswell, Geddes and Scholten (2011, p.1) employ the term ‘policy narratives.’ The authors emphasize three criteria that narratives must meet to be successful: they must be cognitively plausible, dramatically or morally compelling, and resonate with perceived interests.

Spatial narratives constitute a reservoir of knowledge on space as well as ways of constructing space and places by introducing certain notions, events, and characters (Opiłowska, 2019, pp. 103–104). Narratives may also contain references to practices or activities maintained in space and places. By exploring the relations between narratives and borderlands’ space and meaningful places, three areas will be considered:

- the role of a narrative in constructing space and places through narrating it (Fischer-Nebmaier, 2015, p. 33);
- space is a dynamic ‘auditory’ in which narratives can be heard, shaped and retold -and at the same time a stage for non-verbal or non-word-centered activities undertaken on stage, that is, mundane lived practices, performances or artistic interventions (Michałowska, 2014), which can be treated as a particular type of a narrative of such collective activities as electoral campaigns, demonstrations, marches, processions, pageants, or actions may contain narrative content (cf. Lam-Knott, 2020) or be inscribed in particular ways of narrating places, for example a city or a riverside;
- material effects of narrative practices embodied in borderlands’ heritage and thus space and place become a carrier of a narrative. The spatial narratives at multiple scales may also overlap and contradict each other, for example a state’s public narratives of places may contradict with local narratives. It is also important to consider the temporal perspective along with layering, obscuring, obliterating, re-reading, and refreshing meanings (palimpsest).

Individual narratives are stories told by borderlands’ inhabitants. In narrating the lack of or presence of the border in their everyday life, the individuals will provide a varied representation of their biographical experiences. Each time, the narrative expresses the relation between individuals and the social and spatial world, while constructing and justifying it. The essence of individual narratives is individual experience and understanding, while they simultaneously play a crucial role in the process of creating the stories themselves. Therefore, experiencing reality, while participating in specific cultural patterns, is ‘primary.’ Individual narratives include comprehensive ‘life stories’ as well as ‘fragmentary’ (topic-related) autobiographies constructed around a plot of particular importance for the narrator—an aspect of his or her own life. Storytelling, however, is not only an element of creating places and defining ways of perceiving space but also has pre-configurative potential for determining how borderlands are imagined and conceived (Lam-Knott, 2020, p. 95). When focusing on the individual stories of ‘people,’ including people of different gender, young people and national

minorities, and the collective stories through which individual people make sense of the world, B-SHAPES employ the ‘narrative from the ground’ approach.

Applying the study of narratives to the issue of Europe’s perceptions has its challenges. We might approach them by scrutinizing the three dimensions of narratives above. In the case of public narratives, we may adhere to much discussed controversy on who is the European public, or *demos*, and where it could speak? Where is the European public sphere, and what is its relation to public spheres of nation states? ‘The European public’ is the contested field in which different actors – the EU, governments, local administration, media, social movements, or NGOs overlap and participate in the struggle to define its shape. Less a separate domain with its own scope and structures, the European public sphere is composed of overlapping and competing layers and forces. It does not “emerge above and beyond local-, national-, or issue-specific public sphere in some abstract supra-national space but rather through Europeanisation of these various public spheres” (Risse, 2010; Risse 2015, p. 3). Thus, the specific sites of public narratives on Europe are far from self-evident and cannot be detected in advance. Each public narrative on Europe takes part in the construction of the European public sphere.

The spatial narratives on Europe also face specific obstacles. If in the case of a city, region or nation-state it is possible to treat territorial, administrative, ethnic or historical boundaries as co-ordinates which help to map the space and the place of the subject in it, then the spatial narratives on Europe are marked by the well-known and ongoing disputes around the ‘true’ boundaries of Europe. The lack of clear delimitation of Europe and the ever-changing character of its borders makes European space even more deterritorialized and fleeting than other spatial entities. European space seems not to exist ‘objectively’ outside the processes of its narrativization – the narrative of its borders is groundless, or “from nowhere” (Robinson, 2007).

And, finally, the task of creating individual narrative in Europe is haunted by the often-evoked questions concerning the European identity: What does it mean to be a European? Is it identity which is analogous to national, regional or ethnic ones, or does it differ? And especially, how might it differ in the borderlands – areas with their identity troubles? The European dimension in individual narratives brings a potential split into other forms of identification and belonging – be they national, macro- and micro-regional (Svensson and Nilson, 2023), local, cosmopolitan, ethnic, class or ideological – making them “multi-layered, dynamic and fluid” (Ivic, 2016)

These challenges should not result in resignation. On the contrary, they even reinforce our assumption that border narratives are socially constructed, floating and contested, and they find their materializations and inscriptions in various forms of meaning. In the next section, we discuss macro narratives on Europe which are focused on borders and their role in defining Europe. As will be seen, there is a rich and heterogeneous tradition of thinking about Europe from its borders: as borderland entity. We would like to refer to it as reservoir of border macro-narratives on Europe and to test if and how they are present in our research material.

2. Europe and border macro-narratives

Starting from the foregoing observations it can be argued that conceptualisations of the European public sphere, European space or European identity suffer from remarkably similar challenges – the issue of their delimitation. In each case there is some uncertainty about or indecision on how to map and identify ‘Europe.’ It is as if the border problem was part of the core of the concept of Europe. In this section we follow influential narratives on Europe to demonstrate that thinking about Europe is always combined with theorising borders. It is not necessary to include border aspects to study Europe – as we have to do with, for example, climate, migration, post-colonies, or other neglected factors. This is so because Europe and border are so closely intertwined that the former cannot be defined without the latter. From its beginnings in the Greek antiquity, there was an inclination to understand the idea of Europe as a transgressive narrative of universalism which is destined to overcome boundaries of particularism like nation, ethnicity, identity, religion (Delanty, 1995). At the same time, the justification of an exceptional European destiny to transgression required to distinguish it from its various ‘Others’: savages, barbarians, non-Westerners, backward civilisations or peripheral nations (Dainotto, 2007).

This ambiguity of the European idea is not purely abstract, contemplative problem - it has its repercussion in very concrete disputes about Europe. Should we understand it as a planetary civilisation, or a parochial culture; is it a territorial domain, or a force of deterritorialization; are we to regard it as one identity among many (e.g. American, Chinese), or as a deconstructive move against any stable identity; how to think about the borders of Europe – as lines of exclusion, demarcated against its Others, or as constantly renegotiated thresholds of hospitality and inclusion?

It seems that Europe is, as it is well summarised by Rodolphe Gasché (2021), always something more than itself (universal civilisation bigger than its carrier) and – in parallel – something less than it claims to be (not even a continent, country, or real territorial entity of any kind). The tension between “being more” and “being less” can be reduced to the most basic binary oppositions: particularism/universalism, identity/difference, territory/transgression (Lindberg, Prozorov and Ojakangas, 2014). Every claim of Europe to be “more than it is,” or to represent true universalism is – eventually – unmasked as false pretence or imperialism in disguise. Such exposure of flawed universality of Europe does not result in its reduction to one particularism among many and does not give Europe its fixed meaning and scope (Balibar, 2002, p. 100). This mechanism – of missed universalisation and impossible particularisation – leaves Europe in an in-between zone, as a split “borderline” concept (Balibar, 2003, p. 322).

What we intend to adapt from conceptualisations of European idea is the most general statement that European narratives are inherently border narratives. As it was well observed by Klaus Eder (2006, p. 269): “borders of Europe [...] depend on [...] shared stories about its

boundaries". The author claims that the institutionalised shape of Europe is developed through a continuous or discontinuous process of narration on European borders which temporarily close the narrative only to establish its new openings.

Narrative bordering concerns not only big stories on the European history, politics or integration. It takes part also in micro-narratives which are responsible for creating and maintaining the identity of the subject and his/her sense of meaning. Each act of subjective narration in social reality of Europe is associated with the effort to map that reality and then to inscribe the narrator in it. And mapping Europe would be impossible without mental, imaginative or conceptual (de/re)bordering.

Considering recent re-borderings at external as well as internal borders of Europe/the EU it seems timely to examine if and how re-ramifications of borders may result in changes of perceptions of Europe. Borderlanders – as those who live closest to the borders and experience them in their everyday lives – could be affected the most by contemporary processes of (de/re)bordering. It is because borderlands generate specific influence on its inhabitants, making them agents of innovative attitudes and adaptations to changes (Gołdyka, 2020). From pandemics of COVID-19 and covid-fencing, through external clandestine migration and new walling of borders, to the outbreak of war in Ukraine and the influx of refugees, recent years have provided many stimuli to changes of form, role and location of borders. Be it infection controls and introduction of COVID passports, externalisation of bordering to non-EU countries and their internalisation in the form of biometric, panoptic and juridical devices, or reducing the people on the move to objects of humanitarian care or living weapons in the hybrid war – all Europeans, and especially borderlanders, were faced with rapidly changing social reality. Thus, we may expect that – as was the case in the past – border transformations shape the transformations of perceptions of Europe.

Although it is possible that in such a turbulent period we may approach novel types of narratives in our research, still it is helpful to refer to already existing accounts of recent border narratives in Europe. Since narratives are never constructed by social subjects detached from the public sphere and collective emotions, it is plausible that our respondents will refer to framework that were described by scholars in recent years. Our overview of narratives also has the merit of establishing common notions that will be applied in the data analysis. All border narratives that we introduce below have the advantage of understanding Europe as an inherently borderline notion: not something which is given in advance, but contested, negotiated, constructed differently, depending on the specific mechanisms of bordering that contribute to (re/de)construction of Europe. As will be shown below, the given narrative on borders belongs to a wider narrative on Europe (as borderland).

Crucially, border narratives should not be conceived of as detached from the everyday life of people who have the experience of living at the border or approaching the border. They are not stories told above the heads of the people. What is told and what is lived meets in border narratives because borders are performed and they might be maintained only as long as they are performed (Kaiser, 2012, pp. 522-524). Pickering (2006, p. 45) claims that "borders are

performed to multiple audiences and produce not only a range of words, languages and codes to communicate their location and function, but also the border itself". Narratives confirm the existence of the border and its concrete mode of functioning, but they might also challenge them, consciously or not, deliberately or incidentally.

We adopted six border narratives on Europe to develop the initial framework for analysis of the research data. These six narratives help us to distinguish different relations of borders and Europe. They described the dynamics between border transformations and their impact on the visions of Europe. In what follows, we provide an overview of following narratives: (1) the narrative of crisis of/in Europe; (2) the narrative of the (in)visibility of borders; (3) the narrative of the (in)securitisation of borders; (4) the narrative of the (auto)immunological crisis of borders; (5) the narrative of (in)humanitarian bordering; (6) the narrative of contesting borders in the name of Europe. The list is far from comprehensive, but we believe that it is helpful as working framework which grasps the most important border metamorphoses in Europe.

2.1 The narrative of crisis of/in Europe

"Crisis" has become one of the buzzwords in contemporary Europe. The vocabulary of "falling into crisis," "being in crisis," "recovering from crisis," "overlapping of diverse types of crises," "crisis as a call to change," "crisis as opportunity" is widespread in public discourses in Europe. From the financial crisis in 2007-8 to the debt crisis in the Eurozone, from the perceived crisis of social cohesion, precarity and youth unemployment, from ecological crisis to pandemic crisis, or from a crisis of values to a crisis of European integration – the list could be extended (New Keywords Collective, 2016). We are interested in the crisis narrative around borders of Europe – that "our borders are in crisis," that there is a "humanitarian crisis at the borders," a "security crisis in controlling borders and migration," or a "crisis of integration resulting from the border crisis," and so on.

Although the crisis narratives on Europe are very varied and they refer to issues belonging to various aspects of social reality, we could – following analysis by New Keywords Collective (2016) – assign them to two broad categories. On the one hand, we have the narratives of crisis happening in Europe, which means: felt in Europe, brought to Europe, suffered by Europe, haunting Europe, etc. What these narratives have in common is that Europe is here the stage on which the crisis is happening, or the mere passive receptor of processes leading to crises. These narratives lead to the perception that crisis comes to Europe from elsewhere, be it financial markets which became too complicated and multi-layered to be controllable, migratory movements which put pressure on the borders, or disease germs – physical or mental – disintegrating Europe. Borders have distinct roles to play in narratives of crisis IN Europe: they are responsible for defending and protecting against external threats and crisis tendencies. To make Europe is to take back control over what is ours: territory, security,

identity, resources. Various kinds of re-bordering – from walling the boundaries, reducing the possibilities of legal migration, introducing biometric passports, defending European values through tighter identities, or proliferating borders inside and outside of Europe, also in new fleeting and invisible forms – are considered as means to liberate Europe from crisis.

On the other hand, New Keywords Collective (2016) distinguishes the second bigger type of narrative: the crisis of Europe. The rhetorical difference between speaking of “crisis in Europe” and “crisis of Europe” might be regarded as splitting hairs. But, in fact, it offers a vastly different story about borders and Europe. Instead of promoting a binary account of things taking place in Europe or out of Europe, it frees us from the logic of “Us” and “Them,” “here” and “there,” “health” and “pathogens.” Crisis is no longer seen as a foreign attack on Europe, but as a state caused by Europe itself, or sometimes even in the name of (a specific vision of) Europe. Crisis is – in these kinds of stories – resulting from decisions taken in Europe, related to European integration, or understood as a symptom of unsolved European issues. It is thus not possible to save Europe from an external crisis logic, but it is necessary to reform Europe in such a way that it could be able to stop generating and provoking crises and become better equipped to deal with them.

Borders, as one of the state instruments to tackle crisis, cease to be the instruments of retaining or regaining an “authentic,” “healthy” Europe against anomalies and pathologies. Instead of being a solution to the issues coming to Europe, they are a part of the problem contributing to the crisis of Europe. Border regimes do not provide a solution to the crisis issues – they take important part in causing them. By forcing people on the move to take more dangerous routes to get to Europe, to hire smugglers, or desperately storming the security fences, these regimes produced the crises that they are designed to solve. In result, the borderlands of Europe become the focus point in the crisis narratives. The spectacular and mediatized way to portray migrants as the root of the crisis of Europe obscures the European responsibility for its regimes of circulation of people. Closures of border crossings, walling of territories, or security operations in the sea suggest to the public opinion that Europe is sieged and attacked by dangerous invaders. The change of narrative from “the crisis in Europe” to “the crisis of Europe” offers a way to reorient the gaze from migrants as the cause of the crisis to people on the move as the symptom of European border regimes. It also helps to extend the focus from territorial borders as the main site of the crisis to wider processes of de/re-bordering inside and outside of the EU.

In our research, we intend to analyse how borderlanders understand the connection between borders, crisis and Europe. Is there a border crisis? What is its nature? Who or what is responsible for its course? How to react to the crisis? Are borders in crisis, or is it the crisis produced by a malfunctioning of borders?

2.2 The narrative of (in)visibility of borders

Although it might be expected that it is the historical privilege of people who live close to the state border – the borderlanders – to experience its functioning in the everyday life, from today’s perspective this point of view is not so self-evident. On the one hand, it is because internal borders in the EU have become less visible – or visible in separate ways than walls, fences, towers, or border crossings (Hagen and Diener, 2022). The end of the Cold War, the extension of the Schengen area, and the abolition of permanent border checks between member states can potentially weaken the shadow of the border in the lives of borderlanders. On the other hand, if the narrative of Europe as “freedom of movement” celebrates the dissolution of internal hard borders, it is supplemented by an impressive proliferation and multiplication of borders both in and nearby Europe (Müller, 2014). From walling off and enforcing the external borders of the EU, through diffusing and extending border controls to the outside world, to developing new subtle and seemingly invisible methods of bordering inside the EU – the epistemic privilege of seeing the border by borderlanders was redistributed to many different subjects who face borders in their everyday lives (Mezzadra and Neilson, 2013). Be it an illegalised migrant without status and documents, a transgender person struggling to prove his/her identity during passport control, a racialised migrant arousing vigilance of police patrol while walking in a rich neighbourhood, or a borderlander suffering from the sudden closing of the border during pandemics – the border appears in many forms in flexible and often unexpected ways. We thus may speak of parallel processes of gaining visibility and invisibility of borders in contemporary Europe.

Yet, we must ask: gaining or losing visibility to whom? Borders may be invisible for some people, giving them feeling of living in a “borderless world.” Or their presence could be overwhelming and permanent, resulting in the sensation of gated reality. They can also be seen or unseen in a particular way. As it was noted by Brambilla (2021), visibility and invisibility can give or take away agency from border dwellers and border crossers. It is a mechanism called by Jacques Ranciere (2013) a distribution of the sensible: deciding on what/who is seen and unseen, who counts as a political subject, what can be said, who can act legally and materially, etc.

Sometimes being visible is a sign of privilege, sometimes a curse. The same goes with invisibility – it can give power to act, move and live freely, or it could result in exclusion, marginalisation and the lack of rights. Seeing a border could mean seeing the wall, the guards or bureaucratic measures, or it could mean seeing the open path, a route to work, or a memory from the past. And unseeing a border might mean, on the one hand, overlooking its presence during everyday commuting, forgetting about it, or being unconscious of the fate of those who do not have the privilege to believe that they belong to a “borderless world”; and on the other hand, it might be the courage to ignore borders and act in the shadows, the ignorance of the risk to cross them, or the lack of knowledge of the consequences of being stopped and arrested.

The perceptions of border are thus structured in relation to ethnicity, class, status, identity, and/or lifestyle. Not only are borders (in)visible to different subjects, but they also provide visibility and invisibility, or distinct types of visibility and invisibility, to different people and movements. When borders became elastic, moving, and diffused, it became hard to determine in advance which borders are visible and which are not (and to whom). The same could be said about the illuminating character of borders: who is seen by the border and how (Rumford, 2014, p. 39). Some policies of re-enforcing borders rest on hiding them from the view of the European public or making them less detectable for people who intend to cross borders. The opposite may also be true: walling of borders, states of emergency or mediated deportations may be signs of “border spectacles” in which authorities try to demonstrate their sovereignty and agency, but they may go hand in hand with more open borders to economic migrants, or with distracting the public view from the issue of migrants’ illegalisation (De Genova, 2015).

How borders are (in)visible and to whom are questions that contribute to a public demonstration of who may belong to Europe. In our research we would like to remain sensitive to nuanced ways in which borderlanders narrate about what borders they see, where when and how. From a bottom-up perspective the phenomenology of European borders might be multi-sensed and even contradictory: open and closed, present as open and present as closed, open to some and closed to others, stable and porous, permanent and temporary, fixed and shifting, external and internal, material and immaterial, institutional and natural, socially constructed and objectively given, etc.

2.3 The narrative of (in)securitisation of borders

Why, despite renewed attempts in recent years to make borders tighter and more securitised, do those political decisions not necessarily lead to the rise of ontological security provided by borders? How to explain the way in which securitisation gives the EU’s citizens more insecurity and border anxieties? In the empirical study conducted by the team led by Nick Vaughan-Williams (2021), 179 people from 11 cities in the EU participated in group interviews to share their views about “border crisis”. The scholars analysed the researched material to describe vernacular narratives of the EU’s citizens on how they feel about borders’ transformations and policy changes. Leaving aside detailed differences that exist between Europeans, we would like to focus on a wider narrative which come out top during the group interviews.

Vaughan-Williams (2021), in his book summary of the research, states that vernacular border narratives are caught in the vicious circle of securitisation and in-securitisation. Thus, the EU’s citizens – regardless of their political views and specific observations about borders – are convinced that they live in times of border crisis. In such times, strategies of re-bordering, securitisation of borders, and taking back control of migration flows, are presented in public discourse by politicians and commentators as remedies for insecurity and border anxieties. However, the implementation of these strategies and the spectacular way in which they are

discussed in the media, do not lead to the rise of security. The viewpoint that borders are in permanent crisis becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy: if borders still need strengthening and walling, then the reasons to feel fear are still there.

Securitisation of borders – building fences, increasing the size of a police force, or organising mediatised spectacles of guarding boundaries or deporting illegals – functions not as a sign of force or control, but as proof of the impotence of authorities. This contributes to the development of a vicious circle of ontological (in)security because of borders' ramifications: border anxieties cause re-bordering and securitisation, which create even more border anxieties – so more re-bordering and securitisation is needed, and so on.

Ontological insecurity, enhanced by excessive securitisation, is triggered also by the lack of access to expertise and reliable information about borders, migration and the EU's policies. Securitisation of borders means that the border tensions are relegated from the public view or presented by way of a border spectacle: migrants' raids on border fences, boats capsizing in the sea, or public demonstrations of strong national sovereignty. "Gated ignorance" is one of the by-products of the securitisation of borders. When fear, sensations and conspiracy theories accompany these processes, then bordering leads to othering. Those 'on the other side' are represented as terrorists, sexual harassers, or human-animals, making it even easier to demand more securitisation to stop these "dangerous subjects" at the gates of Europe. And the political climate of a besieged "fortress Europe" favours not only the enforcement of external borders, but also legitimises the strengthening of both internal and everyday bordering.

At the end of the circle, Europe is gated from the outside and from within, something, which affects the levels of border anxieties among citizens. The rise of re-bordering deepens the feeling that societies live under pressures that must be alleviated by further re-bordering – so the circle starts anew. In our research, we would like to check if any signs of the spiral of (in)securitisation is present among borderlanders. Can we say that securitisation of borders brings more (perceived) security? Or does it rather reproduce and expand the problem which it intended to solve?

2.4 The narrative of (auto)immunological crisis of borders

Interestingly, the paradox in which the desire for more protection and walling-off from the outside results in the destruction of the very qualities that were supposed to be defended by re-bordering, is sometimes conceptualised in terms of "autoimmunological crisis." Vaughan-Williams (2015) proposed regarding Europe's border crisis through an immunological paradigm even before the COVID-19 pandemic induced directly immunological bordering. This paradigm was theoretically developed in "*A Philosophy for Europe*" by Roberto Esposito (2018) in which he diagnosed – also before the pandemics – that a European inclination for separation from the external world through new kinds of borders, leads Europe to a risk

similar to autoimmune disease. As with living organisms, when the obsessive drive to remain protected against other organisms causes the self-weakening and lack of immunity, so too is too much closure not necessarily beneficial in maintaining the well-being of political bodies. Esposito is especially interested in how the intention to defend European liberties and way of life through re-bordering, creates the measures of control which are so harsh and serious that they undermine these European values. In this way, it is Europe – not its others – that poses the greatest threat to itself. The only possibility to avoid autoimmune disorder was, for Esposito, gaining immunity through the development of antibodies – and this could be done only through responsible contact with the outside. In other words, it would mean to invent some strategies of de-bordering – understood not necessarily as complete abolition of borders, but as creation of beneficial borders as meeting places.

Departing from Esposito's proposals, what matters for us is to determine if and how immunological narratives are to be found among borderlanders. Do they see borders and Europe in terms of health and disease, body and pathogens, immunity and infection? How do they evaluate different strategies of becoming immune – from re-bordering and securitisation to hybridisation and mutual exchange? These issues are important when examining bordering as othering in cultural terms – how might borders lead to racialisation, orientalism, demonisation, or a romanticisation of Europe and non-Europe, Us and Them, citizens and denizens, etc.?

However, with pandemics, the vocabulary of immunity, pathogens, or autoimmune disorder became something more than a metaphorical exercise. European borders indeed took on a biopolitical character. Old borders – those that were created to contain “human foreign bodies” - were utilized and transformed to deal with “non-human foreign bodies.” In fact, the difference between those two categories became blurred since it was the people on the move who were seen as carriers of the virus. New immunological borders were also created on many levels – starting from parcellation of infected state or regional territories, from introducing quarantines in enclosed institutions and households, checking certificates of vaccinations, to internalizing self-control or self-bordering by individuals. This had special significance for those living in the borderlands who cross the border on their route to work, family or education. During the pandemic, the possibility to do so was limited or fully undermined. In the academic discourse this re-bordering crisis (Opitowska and Weber, forthcoming) has been framed as a “global nationalism” (Bieber, 2020), an “era of post-globalisation” (Konrad, 2021), the “advent of unilateralism” (Böhm, 2021b) or “covid-fencing” (Medeiros *et al.*, 2021).

The spread of immunological borders prompts us also to ask about the way in which this phenomenon reinforced or weakened earlier border narratives. We should here address issues of othering, racializing and demonizing of “undeserving migrants” during pandemics, but also, the opposite scenario in which covid-re-bordering raised the longing for a more open or borderless Europe might be considered as well. Recognizing the importance and timeliness of the immunological aspect of borders, one of our aims will be to study if and how

borderlanders saw the presence of immunological borders during the pandemic? Which processes are regarded by them as aspects of covid-bordering? How did the appearance of dangerous pathogens affect their narratives on borders and Europe?

2.5 The narrative of (in)humanitarian borders

One of the worrying implications of the securitisation of borders is the inhumane treatment of migrants and human rights violations and deprivation through new security measures. Migrants injured by barbed wires, dehydrated and suffering hunger because of long journeys avoiding border controls, drown in the sea or are at the mercy of traffickers – these issues became a big concern in debates around border policies in Europe. No wonder that humanitarian narratives became widespread as a reaction to rising securitisation. The ethical response may be regarded as a counterproposal to re-bordering, but – following Pallister-Wilkins (2022) - we might see these two tendencies – of securitisation and humanitarianism – as two sides of the same coin. The narrative of “saving lives” and “protecting human rights” - while formulated as lofty and idealistic – is supplementary to the narrative of “making our borders tighter” and “being tough on migration.” The lives that must be saved from deaths, injuries or risks, are the same lives that became vulnerable through securitisation. It is the stripping of people off their political rights and agency which reduces them to the “naked life” (Agamben, 1998), the passive victim and recipient of mercy of “good Europeans”. Humanitarianism does not challenge the mechanism of depriving people on the move of their political subjectivity – it is content with taking care of those who are disempowered, dispossessed, or depoliticized (Fassin, 2011). And borders play a key role in this double act of securitisation/dehumanisation and humanitarianism/depoliticization through which unequal mobility is produced and maintained in Europe.

Thus, humanitarianism does not provide the way out of a vicious circle of securitisation. On the contrary, it is easily reinscribed in it. More securitisation results in more demands of humanitarian actions. And more humanitarian actions are the proof that there is a security crisis at the borders. And if there is a security crisis, then the more securitisation is needed. According to Vaughan-Williams (2015) the tension between two opposite values in bordering – bringing security and providing human rights – in some cases is so intertwined that it is almost impossible to find out which is which. The strategies are blurred also in border policies. Should we understand border policing as securitisation of borders against people on the move, or are such operations focused primarily on saving lives? Are borders militarised to fight human trafficking and offer security to their potential victims, or they contribute to the rise of smuggling because of creating less opportunities to cross borders in legal ways?

We will endeavour to better understand how humanitarian borders narratives operate among borderlanders. Do these demand humanitarian borders of Europe, and, if so, what do they mean by this notion? How do they try to navigate between securitisation and

humanitarianism? Do they see an inhumane treatment of migrants at the borders, and how does this affect their evaluation of Europe? How do they understand the European ethical responsibility? Is it expressed in the language of humanitarian obligation, or is it more political critique of Europe or of the European idea?

2.6 The narrative of contesting borders (in the name of Europe?)

Beyond securitisation and humanitarianism, the border crisis also evokes a narrative of self-criticism of Europeans. If securitisation is the strategy of enforcing and defending the shape of Europe, and humanitarianism is a supplementary response to the excesses caused by this particularism, then self-criticism acts as means to reinvigorate the universalist promise of European idea. Europe as the idea of a borderless world, cosmopolitanism, or transgression of parochial boundaries functions in militant narratives of both progressively oriented citizens of Europe and activists (Blokker, 2022), and some newcomers to Europe who express their belief in the universality of European values of freedom and equality for all (Tazzioli, 2014).

On the other hand, a different self-critique narrative is expressed not in the name of (a better, authentic, idealist) Europe, but against Eurocentrism (De Genova, 2016). Focused on post-colonial, neo-imperialist, racist or exploitative relations between Europe and its outside, this narrative unmasks bordering as a European strategy to maintain privileges. Leaving for the moment aside the difference between criticizing Europe in the name of Europe or doing it against it, it is worth noting that what these strategies have in common is the repudiation of “fortress Europe.”

What must be differentiated is also the criticism of Europe and the criticism of the EU. While sometimes they might be equated – when the EU is understood as the avatar of Europe – in other cases they will differ. Thus, being pro-European and being pro-EU should not be treated as identical. And when it comes to European borders, the responsibility for their functioning and policies might be attributed by the people to authorities from various levels – not exclusively to the EU.

In our project our aim is to examine if and how borderlanders challenge the existing manifestation of European borders and to determine what role Europe (and the EU) play in these challenges. Do borderlanders regard Europe/EU as the part of the problem or part of the solution? Do they demand more Europe or less in border policies? How contemporary policies affected their viewpoints on Europe? Is Europe seen from borderlands more as a fortress, or a transgressive idea?

To propose common notions for the analysis, we would like to distinguish two axes: 1) the level on which borderlanders see the borders (from European through the EU, national, sub-national to individual); 2) the type of border narrative which they use when speaking of

borders. The Table 1 combines these two axes to provide the basic framework for cataloguing the border narratives on Europe.

	European	EU	National	Sub-national	Individual
Lack of borders / Comeback of borders					
Open borders / Closed borders					
Enforced borders / Transgressed borders					
Borders as walls / Borders as filters					
Territorialized borders / Deterritorialized borders					
External borders / Internalized borders					
Material borders / Immaterial borders					
Bordering visibility /invisibility					
Bordering as Othering / Bordering as hospitality					
Europeanization as re-bordering / Europeanization as de-bordering					
Supporting bordering /Challenging bordering					

Table 1. Border narratives on Europe

3. Border as lenses: perceptions of Europe

The key assumption of B-SHAPES is that borders shape people's perception of Europe. As the six macro narratives elaborated above have shown, the concepts and imagery of borders and Europe are closely intertwined and construct each other. As it should be clear from our brief review of border narratives on Europe, we treat borders as phenomena which are under construction – shifting, differentiating, multi-dimensional. In studying border narratives, we intend to grasp the heterogeneity and elasticity of borders as they are seen by borderlanders. Following Balibar (2009a), we understand the ever-unfinished work of delineation-signification-materialisation of Europe in crossing and folding activities as ongoing processes of translation. When people are crossing and folding, hegemonic spatial border-logics expressed in institutional and media discourse influencing state policies and the EU such as the six master-narratives described above, would stand out as important. Such border logics do work in people's perceptions used to order the reality Europe is, supposedly.

However, we also intend to investigate the crossing and folding away from predetermined logics and as mundane perceptions of Europe, thus distancing ourselves from normative discussions and entering a space, which is relationally and practically 'already there' – at the same time as it is 'in the making' and 'not yet there'. Here, the trick is for us to read border logics as making possible, not just one coherent logic, but, thinking relationally, show how multiple Europes express in perceptions, connecting multiple versions of spatial-territorial dimensions to Europe with the folding of identifications and their boundaries. We do not intend to finally locate perceptions of Europe or what it is to be European, nor specify what the boundaries are that capture its meaning. Rather, we make explicit how Europe is constantly folding in material-discursive processes involving multiple, relational ontologies, negotiated, contradicting and conflictual, and always in the making. To additionally recognise the productivity involved in these crossing and folding activities, we will illustrate how perceptions in relation to mundane, ambiguous everyday-life performances – the never-ending struggles about what Europe is, should and might be, perceptions entangled with the ongoing performance and becoming of Europe (Andersen and Sandberg, 2020; Andersen and Aubry, 2022).

Grasping such crossing and folding of Europe in entanglements of people's (and other actant's) narrative perceptions imply a close-up and sustained study enabled only by being attentive to as well as grasping Europe as processes of becoming. It is against this backdrop, we explore the perception of Europe through the lens of borderlands from three specific perspectives – Euroscepticism, border landscapes as heritage and minorities living in borderlands which are considered as 'change agents.' In this way B-SHAPES will apply a novel and dynamic understanding of borders focusing on individual stories of people and their agency.

3.1. Euroscepticism and borderlands

Narratives are a relatively recent addition to the toolkit of Euroscepticism studies. Political scientists initially developed the concept of Euroscepticism by identifying it as a British phenomenon entering the political arena in the 1980s, notably with Margaret Thatcher's rejection of the European Economic Community (EEC) (Spiering, 2004; Harmsen and Spiering, 2004). Theorists concentrated for a long time on Euroscepticism as a political phenomenon appearing in certain countries, such as the United Kingdom or some of the Scandinavian states, but also as being confined largely to the marginal, extreme right of left spectrum of political parties (Taggart, 1998). Focusing primarily on classification of political parties, they identified two types of opposition to Europe: the rejection of the principle underlying European integration itself (hard Euroscepticism) and opposition against its form of realization by the EEC and later by the European Union (EU) (soft Euroscepticism) (Szczerbiak and Taggart, 2008; Kopecky and Mudde, 2002).

From the 2000s onwards, researchers on Euroscepticism have studied how opposition to Europe was constructed within certain national political spaces in the EEC/EU and increasingly focused their research on "cultural and historical variables" (Neumayer, Zalewski and Roger, 2008; Dargent, 2002) by analysing national discourses on European integration (Harmsen, 2008; Diez Medrano, 2003; Theiler, 2004; Cautrès, 2000; Vignaux, 2004). However, researchers in this field of study also realized that Euroscepticism seemed too narrow as a term to englobe all sorts of anti-European attitudes and that the early studies had too intricately linked the origins of Euroscepticism to British opposition to European integration in the 1980s (Crespy and Verschueren, 2010). Indeed, considering historical studies of Eurosceptic narratives in other countries in the 1960s and 1970s (Lang, 2010; Bitsch, 2010) the terminology had to be reviewed so as to broaden the concept of what it means to "be against Europe". This has given rise to a series of other terms that have been used in order to denote ever growing sub-categories of Euroscepticism: Euro-pessimism, Euro-phobia, Euro-rebellion, Euro-indifference (Delmotte, 2007; Rozenberg, 2007), Euro-realism (Neumayer, 2007), critical Europeanism (Della Porta, 2006) or Euro-cynicism (Abst and Krouwel, 2007) are just some examples of the inflationary sub-terminology used to designate different varieties of Euroscepticism. This terminological differentiation has suffered from a "theoretical and terminological vagueness" (Hamman, 2010) which was sometimes cultivated on purpose. It allowed indeed for a conciliation of apparently vastly different and non-convergent elements of the "no" to Europe, thus making it possible to use a range of different terms to describe the same phenomenon.

Beyond the proliferation of novel words for the same phenomenon, the terminology developed also seemed to suggest that there are truly objective ways how to classify diverse types and actors of Euroscepticism. However, in many cases, we are dealing with narratives

about specific aspects of European integration (Pasquinucci, 2020; Csehi and Zgut, 2020; Hloušek and Havlík, 2023) and a series of negative emotions (Frank, 2004; Girault, 1994). Some examples tie in with the master-narratives identified above, including the narrative of crisis, the narrative of border securitization, and immunological narratives and include the fear of globalisation, the fear of the loss of one's job, of a social Europe, the anger about the Brussels bureaucracy with innumerable European directives complicating the daily life and habits of the European people, but also the disillusionment with a Europe that has not become a reality for the citizens, despite promises and political discourses.

Importantly, the research focus has been widened to include not only party-political narratives – what, in the style of Euroscepticism's sister field of populism, one might term the 'demand side' - but also focused on bottom-up perspectives, with a growing emphasis on individual and public narratives as employed by the citizens. Euroscepticism now seems a political and social phenomenon, which is frequently expressed by certain components of the European population (Loth and Barthel, 2007; Delmotte, 2007, p. 544).

In this light, one narrative that is particularly relevant to Euroscepticism is that of a lack of democratic legitimacy or closeness to the citizens that emerged in the 1990s. The original theories on Euroscepticism could not explain the end of the "permissive consensus" on the principle of European unification i.e., the end of the passive acceptance of this process by the European citizens (Lindberg and Scheingold, 1970) after the Maastricht Treaty was signed in 1992. From then on, the growing demand for covering up the democratic deficit resulted in decreasing public support of the European integration process (Manigand and Dulphy, 2004). Many researchers working on Euroscepticism then identified a growing aversion to the EU expressed by the European population and this could also lead to blockages in the EU institutions themselves (Brack and Costa, 2014).

It is worth highlighting here that Euroscepticism as a social, rather than merely party political, 'demand side' phenomenon is often, though not always, indicative of hard Euroscepticism, i.e., principled opposition to the European project on democratic grounds. Explanations for this increase in Euroscepticism in the 1990s ranged from an alleged lack of democratic legitimacy of European institutions, an ever-growing distance between the Brussels bureaucracy and the European citizens to the accusation of the EU being elitist and the failure of its political leaders to make the European organisation comprehensible and approachable for the population (Rambour, 2016). According to Liesbet Hooghe and Gary Marks (2008), the loss of the "permissive consensus" then led to a political climate of "constraining dissensus" where Euroscepticism became a generalized phenomenon concerning large parts of the population in Europe and being frequently expressed in elections and referendums.

At the same time, there are clear elements of soft Euroscepticism at play in popular Euroscepticism, where the critique is of specific manifestations of European integration. For

example, “utilitarian” theories of European integration consider support of or opposition to the EU as being a matter of an economic cost-benefit analysis (Mc Laren, 2002; Gabel, 1998). According to these theories, Euroscepticism ties in with narratives of individuals not benefitting from European integration or of this process potentially even presenting a threat to them, for example, if they might lose their employment or their social standards in the wake of a liberalised European labour market (Marks and Hooghe, 2004). This means, however, that Euroscepticism becomes an attitude that might prevail among any citizen at any time: everyone might be Euro-sceptic with regards to a certain field of integration (monetary union, political union, etc.) or at a certain moment of the process (the enlargements towards Central and Eastern Europe in 2004 and 2007, for example) (Rambour, 2010). This also means that hardly anyone is integrally Eurosceptic but could be a supporter of some aspects at one point of integration and an opponent of others at another point. Support of or opposition to Europe can then also be more or less linked to narratives of everyone’s personal situation and experience of the European integration process.

This approach to Euroscepticism particularly suits the situation of borderlands and borderlanders. Globally, however, the scientific literature on the link between borders and anti-Europeanism remains limited. Based on the example of cross-border cooperation, which addresses in a comprehensive and integrated manner the problems and challenges specific to border areas and has contributed to their economic and cultural development, it is easy to think that a stronger European identity has emerged in these territories over time. There are however first attempts to specifically look at Euroscepticism in border regions. One of the first studies in this field has been carried out by geographers. Frédéric Durand, Antoine Decoville and Robert Knippschild (2017) have shown that the presence of a border can lead to particular social and economic phenomena, resulting in a negative perception of open borders and European integration. It causes economic, social and ecological tensions, as well as perceptible rejection phenomena. Thus, it may be assumed that the daily perception of the border and its effects, far from resulting in significant Europhilia, can induce repugnance and a feeling of disappointment with Europe (Durand, Decoville and Knippschild, 2017). Indeed, in cross-border regions, where the reality of the EU is experienced daily, Euroscepticism can be more easily identified among actors, who are disappointed by their experience of crossing the border (Beck, 1999). As the sociologist Phillipe Hamman has demonstrated, border commuters are the classical case of a category of the population which might be frustrated by the non-homogenisation of social security and pension schemes of the EU member states, since they personally suffer from this situation (Hamman, 2010). However, the non-integration of the EU also procures advantages for them, for example, if wage differences prevail in the different member states, some can benefit from higher salaries across the border. The attitude of border commuters towards European integration might paradoxically be supporting it on some occasions and rejecting it on others (Hamman, 2009), with different narratives being produced in these different contexts.

Cross-border cooperation itself may have contributed to the construction of a certain form of opposition to Europe. An illustrative example of Euroscepticism among cross-border actors is the case of people who have engaged in cross-border relations or projects and become disillusioned by the lack of intercultural understanding with their partners (Wassenberg, 2010). More recently, links have also been identified between growing populism and Euroscepticism at European borders and in border regions, for example in a collective book edited by Oscar Mazzoleni *et. al.* (2023) and an article on Multiscalar strategies in right-wing populism of West European parties in borderlands (Biancalana et.al., 2023), which might be exacerbated by backsliding democracy tendencies in some member states (Svensson 2021). This seems to indicate that the research on Euroscepticism in border regions moves again in the direction of a focus on political parties and party politics. B-SHAPES seeks to bring the two together by analysing how party-political narratives and popular, public, individual and spatial, narratives interact.

3.2. Border landscapes as lived heritage

To broaden the perspective of people's narrative perceptions, we take inspiration from the post-humanist turn in the social sciences (Ferrando, 2012). In the sciences, humans are most often understood as the primary agents of meaning-making, decision-making, and drivers of large-scale transition (Haraway, 1991). In response to such (often completely un-reflected) assumptions, the post-humanist perspective detaches humans from the centre of knowledge and agency, in attempting to undo the nature—culture and human—animal divides influencing Western modernity at large, thereby opening a path to explore what nonhumans can “teach us about the world” (Haraway, 1991; Ferrando, 2012; Adler-Nissen, 2014; Steinberg and Peters, 2015). B-SHAPES WP5 intends to bring some of the insights of the post-humanist turn to the human-centric field of border studies. Whereas borders are mostly conceptualised as cultural and human constructions, we will move away from human exceptionalism and understand borders as natural-cultural and more-than-human, made in entangled ecologies and multispecies histories. Indeed, borders are not just “lines in the sand” (Parker and Vaughan-Williams, 2009) but are immanent to multilayered processes and everyday ways of living, valuing, and understanding (Andersen and Sandberg, 2012). Borderlines are an expression of dominant situated knowledges that encompass understandings, valuations, and enactments of nature, time, space, and alterity (Haraway, 1991). As onto-ethico-epistemologies, borders have far-reaching consequences. For instance, the Westphalian border logics that endure today reveal a Euro- and human-centric binary understanding of identities and bodies and a conception of nature as land to be conquered and dominated (Ochoa Espejo, 2020). Adopting a posthuman approach to borders is critical for developing more sustainable ways of doing, thinking, and mapping space and inventing more-than-human forms of cosmopolitics (Evans, 2015). Hence, our research attunes to the generative

potential of non-human differences and explores what thinking borders with nonhuman existents can do for border theory, methods, and practice. B-Shapes is in the frontline in the making of “new research agenda for posthuman conversations in border studies” (see Ozguc and Burrige 2023).

Our approach more specifically consists of a narrative study of borderland landscapes as authorized heritage, lived experience and agent of change. Landscape is not a new concept to border studies, rather, there is long tradition of studying border landscapes, including the physical, social, cultural elements of borders (e.g., Rumley and Minghi, 1991/2015; Arreola and Curtis, 1993) and how they are closely related to identity and heritage. As Stephenson (2008: 127) puts it: “cultural identity is strongly associated with the ways in which people interact with their landscapes”, continuing that “a few special landscapes may have ‘universal’ or ‘outstanding’ values, but almost all landscapes will be valued in multiple ways by those people who are closely associated with them.”

Studying the temporal and spatial dimensions of European border landscapes, how they are lived with and perceived by different generations of people and what agencies they bring forth, provides new understanding of how borders shape perceptions of Europe. The border landscape perspective contributes to border studies as well as studies of European identity and heritage by strengthening a dialogue between a place-based approach and identity-based theorisations of borders which is argued to dominate border research today. As Ochoa Espejo (2020) notes, the identities lens, the who-question, “should not be the only established way of understanding politics and designating political institutions (...) we must examine the practices and physical structures that constitute the localised, concrete character of people’s experiences” (Ochoa Espejo, 2020: xi). As an alternative, she proposes a place-based “where” approach to borders where attention is directed from identity politics towards places; shared air, land, and waters.

Landscape as heritage approach highlights relational and progressive understanding of both borders and heritage (Andersen, Opiłowska and Prokkola, forthcoming) and directs attention to both human and non-human agencies, relationship and politics. It departs from an understanding that European and national landscapes and their heritage are not territorially bounded – although heritage is usually constructed this way in national narratives – and should be thought of in relational terms (Massey and Jess, 1995). Compared with the popular borderscapes approach (Strüver, 2005; Gieles and van Houtum, 2012; Brambilla, 2015) that highlights how things and people’s lives straddle across international borders and are not territorially fixed, the landscape approach adds the questions of nature and environment to the study of borders and borderlands by better recognizing the importance of human-non-human relationships.

The landscape approach focuses on how human and natural factors and relationships are lived out and governed in border zones where two or three national systems, jurisdictions and infrastructures meet. The research will create more understanding of how the who- and where questions of borders become entangled in the European border landscapes to

understand the complexity and multiscalar dynamics of European identity and landscape heritage making. Many European borderlands include heritage cultural and natural landscapes that are divided by a state border (Konkoly-Gyuró, Balázs and Tirászi, 2019). Natural heritage, e.g., biodiversity in transboundary areas is often threatened by construction of border infrastructure and differences in land use and policy between neighboring countries that weaken conservation (Liu et al. 2020). European borders are therefore fruitful locations and “laboratories” for examining entanglements and connections between identity, space and place because in these border areas people live near each other, attach with and nourish the same natural and cultural elements, yet at the same time their identity and place narratives may differ considerably. According to a biofilia-hypothesis (Wilson, 1984) humans have inner needs and will to connect with nature and protect the nature for the next generations. However, little is known whether this inner desire is bounded and territorial or relational, for example whether people care more about places that are close to them and what they feel responsible for and in what ways borders shape people’s perception of places worth protecting (see Massey 2004). To gain understanding human-nature connections and perceptions of borderlands, the WP5 research will focus on such elements of culture and nature that are shared at both sides of the border, especially transboundary waters and lands that are understood to form special “objects” of a border landscape in which everyday activities, livelihoods, traditions, and conservation and management practices bring people together across borders (see Häkli, 2009; Fall, 2005) and shape human and non-human interactions.

Border landscapes as an analytical perspective allows us to move beyond “binaries between global and local, humans and nature, self and the other, space and place (Travis, 2020, p. 135), yet acknowledging how border landscapes as lived spaces are often “haunted by the ever-present mapping of the populations in us/them, either/or, here/not there, a mapping of people, which is also constantly brought into being by local talk” (Andersen, 2022). A border landscape perspective connects the identities and place of a border and highlighting the effects of borders and bordering from both human and environmental perspectives, recognizing that there are also conflicts of interest and conflicts related to human activities and utilisation of transboundary waters and ecosystems as a recourse.

Most landscape studies and landscape walk studies focus on “national” or local landscapes, or how transnational communities and migrants and people on the move experience those landscapes that the authorised national and regional narrative highlight as “national” (Tolia-Kelly, 2008), presenting something that is understood as authentic and to give an identity to people who live in the state territory. These landscapes are recognised and constructed in the national and regional authorised landscape catalogues, planning documents etc. (e.g., Linkola, 2015). In comparison, the research of B-SHAPES departs from a notion that a border landscape is as a translocal landscape; people living in and with the landscape may connect the landscape with many real and imagined meanings. Also, they may not conceptualise border landscape

as cosmopolitan and transnational but have more locally and nationally specific understanding and even exclusive perceptions of what and who belongs into the landscape.

The research will therefore also contribute to the multidisciplinary landscape as heritage research by examining how borderlands, as transnational landscapes, are narrativized, experienced and bodily and emotionally sensed. We will examine how is the border narrativized in the visual and work landscape, and what difference the border makes with respect to how diverse groups narrate and experience the lived landscapes and its natural and cultural elements. Methodologically, border landscape can be approached through spatial narratives, both the authorised ones and people's "little narratives" (Prokkola, 2014). Narrative form of knowing and making sense of the world are important for understanding, experiencing, and making the border space. Border landscape narratives will be collected during the *border walks* with different groups of people can be understood as inherently embodied, thus attention is paid also to the capacities of human bodies to traverse, recognise, narrate and 'be' within the landscape (see Tolia-Kelly 2008, p. 118).

The border landscape walking as a method of data collection facilitates the movement into new borderland places, and new spaces of border narratives. Border walks with people can thus be understood to create a "thirdspace of meaning creation through the praxis of walking and talking" (see Moles, 2008; Soja, 1996); "through walking, the researcher and the participant bumble into new narratives, and discover and construct new spaces together as a result" (Moles, 2008, p. 7). When people walk and talk in and about the material elements the borderland, also connecting and drawing on the wider social images and discourses of the border, new understanding, and imaginations of the spatiality of the border space can emerge as well as new identity narratives and conceptions of borders as heritage.

3.3. Narratives of minorities living in borderlands

More than fifty million people living in the European Union belong to a so-called national minority or a minority language community, constituting approximately 11% of the total EU population (Minority Safepack Initiative, 2018). Although these people are categorised as minorities, they are not always small. Indeed, more than 50% of minority groups are composed of 50,000 members or more, sometimes constituting the majority population group in their respective region. Many of them had found themselves as national minorities in newly founded nation-states after the dissolution of the Ottoman and Habsburg empires (Marko and Constantin, 2019). The presence of numerous linguistic and religious groupings on the respective territories prevented the creation of ethnically, linguistically or religiously homogenous nation-states after the collapse of these empires, and the presence of minorities in today's nations continues to challenge monolithic conceptions of nationhood. This cultural diversity that often spans across national borders renders the governance and function of

diverse types of borders, such as linguistic, economic, symbolic and geographic borders and boundaries in border regions particularly complex.

Due to historical border developments particularly after WW1, many minorities now live in the borderlands of states, and many have close relationships with the people living on the other side of the border. This relationship of minorities with borders can be employed as a looking glass through which to investigate re/de-bordering processes in contemporary Europe (Böhm, 2019; Tarvet and Klatt, 2021; Engl, 2022) by using a bottom-up research agenda that puts the emphasis on everyday citizens (Jarvis and Lister, 2013). As described above, Vaughan-Williams (2021) has drawn attention to what is described as a vicious circle of ontological (in)security whereby border anxieties give rise to re-bordering practices and narratives. By giving a voice to everyday people, particularly those at and from the margins, it becomes possible to create counter-narratives that can challenge re-bordering practices and call for a new border politics across Europe.

The complex relationship of minorities with borders plays out in how minorities perceive, experience and negotiate borders' multiple and complex roles, including their use as instruments of state power, identity markers, sites of cooperation, or simply as places of everyday life. States often create, impose, and reinforce borders through arbitrary, coercive and violent processes in response to political, socio-economic and security concerns. The asymmetrical power relations of states and minorities can lead to the marginalisation of minorities in political, socio-cultural, historiographical and economic terms, with borders and (re)bordering policies causing tense relations between what the border means for the minorities and what it symbolizes in nation-state narratives, and as being powerful reminders of past injustices (Balogh, 2019; Bradley and De Noronha, 2022; Mezzadra and Neilson, 2013; Mitterhofer, 2017).

At the same time, the demarcation of local administrative borders of minority regions through autonomy and self-governance can ensure protection and empowerment of minorities and provide a sense of security (Malloy and Palermo, 2015). Borders and the complex histories, politics and symbolism which they embody are key factors in shaping the construction of minority identities against the backdrop of the majority population and for the strengthening of ties within local communities, besides other markers such as culture, language or religion that shape identity boundaries (Konrad, 2020; Carlà, 2022).

Borders are divisive, but they are also crossed. This crossing of political borders is crucial in minority contexts, where transnational ties often lead to active economic, social and culture border crossings. On the one hand, international organisations have developed normative standards that conceive cross-border cooperation as a tool for peacebuilding, conflict resolution and empowerment of minorities (Engl, 2020). On the other hand, minorities are engaged in manifold political and socio-economic transnational practices (Engl, 2020; ECMI Report, 2016). Particularly EU-driven processes of debordering – that is, porous political borders in the single market and transnational engagement of regions in EU-funded regional

cooperation programmes – are crucial for minority groups and stateless nations because they can open new arenas and allies for action (Engl, 2022; Waterbury, 2017).

Finally, for those living in borderlands, borders are also places of everyday interactions and encounters (Berdahl, 1999; Green, 2005; Pelkmans, 2006). Through their narratives of the border, they give insight into how they actively explain, manage, cope with, and challenge the often undesired and difficult consequences of borders on their lives (Mitterhofer, 2017).

The Covid-19 pandemic and the 2015 and 2022 refugee crises have highlighted how states, sub-state entities and supra-state organisations understand, use and manage borders differently. The re-bordering processes and practices that we can observe in critical moments such as these render political, symbolic and cultural boundaries more visible once again, and highlight the mobile, arbitrary, and impermanent nature of borders (Fuller, 2018).

The pandemic revealed the political weakness of border regions faced with the power of nation states and demonstrated the persistence of the “territorial trap” (Agnew, 1994). As Lara-Valencia and Laine argue (2022, p. 673): “territory and territoriality remain vigorous and fitting instruments in the toolbox of nation states as demonstrated by the re-bordering shocks triggered by the coronavirus pandemic across the world.” The re-bordering processes of the pandemic and the migration crisis also emphasises the in-betweenness of minorities in the complex multi-level interactions. It accentuated the continuing relevance and impact of borders as well as minorities’ barriers to participation and representation (Böhm, 2019, 2020; Tarvet and Klatt, 2021; Opilowska, 2021; Wille and Kanesu, 2020). Re-bordering processes have further marginalised the position of both national minorities and migrant populations across Europe, particularly those living in borderlands, as they were often those most impacted by re-bordering decisions taken by the central government without consideration of local needs and circumstances.

The re-bordering process which was sparked by the Covid-19 pandemic and for many borderlands came as ‘unexpected shock’ (Opilowska, 2021) had a number of “hidden costs for national minorities” (Brezigar, 2020): it threatened minority education and linguistic cultural systems (Brezigar, 2020), impacted on minorities’ “borderland lifestyle” more generally (Böhm, 2022; Tarvet and Klatt, 2021), led to the securitisation and the scapegoating of minorities (Carlà, 2022; Eurac Research, 2020), the strengthening of categorical group boundaries between people on either side of the border (Prokkola and Ridanpää, 2022), and negatively affected regional development in borderlands (Böhm, 2021a) as well as cross-border multi-level governance (Klatt, 2020).

However, inhabitants of borderlands should not be considered as passive victims of border politics and narratives. Rather, minorities actively negotiated and resisted state-imposed border restrictions, developing resilience by engaging in adaptive and transformative practices (Prokkola and Ridanpää, 2022). They did so, for instance, by acting as political mediators between states (Engl and Wisthaler, 2020), by engaging in protests and

symbolic acts of solidarity across borders (Opiłowska, 2021), and by highlighting the need for cross-border cohesiveness and solidarity (Juric Pahor, 2020).

4. Conclusion: Border transformations transforming perceptions of Europe?

The report has aimed at creating a coherent theoretical framework for the B-SHAPES project to be able to examine the influence of contested and shifting borders on peoples' perception of Europe and the European project. We argue that narratives are pivotal factors in shaping these perceptions, individual beliefs, attitudes and policies. In the first section we thus discussed multiple conceptualisations of narratives and their applicability in social sciences, encompassing their public, individual and spatial dimensions. Building on a comprehensive literature review, the subsequent section identified six macro narratives related to Europe to be empirically investigated in micro narratives of borderlanders. By assuming that borders play a substantial role in shaping both Europe's identity and people's imaginaries we focus on under-researched actors including Euroscepticism, minorities, as well as the natural and cultural heritage in borderlands. These are regarded as 'change agents' producing micro narratives which might resonate or clash with the macro narratives. Thus, we aim to bridge the gap between grand stories created at the macro level and the grassroots narratives.

Borderlands in nation-states are the sites of dividing and bridging between ethnicities, nations and territories, distinguishing identities of 'Us' and 'Them,' and mediating relationships from conflict to mutuality and exchange, yet, seen from the macro level of Europe, they might be treated as stitches which tie the totality together. It is thus worthwhile to examine the condition of Europe from the borderlands' perspective. What happens with these stitches in the times of dynamic and unexpected transformations of borders? How are these transformations visible in the landscape and viewed by inhabitants of borderlands? Do they influence their perceptions of Europe?

If Europe is really a borderland – as it is believed by many of its leading theorists and ideologues – then it would be a special one. Following Balibar, we could say that it is not only distinguishes itself from other entities – many of its outsides and Others – but, first, it differs from itself, internally. Europe is its own borderland, always troubled questions such as: who am I, where are my borders, to whom I belong, what is my essence, what is my vocation? And by posing these questions – and having to answer them – Europe re-borders and de-borders itself which gives it a possibility to take different faces and shapes. So, if we adopt for the moment the view that Europe might be a borderland, then it is exciting to ask: how it is perceived from its empirical borderlands? And it is even more exciting to dwell into this question when these empirical borderlands shift and are under reconstruction.

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